

HUMAN HEALTH AND SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC FACTORS AFFECTING IT

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Abstract

Man was created in such a way that he has been achieving great heights with his mind and thinking. However, some of our young people who are just starting to grow up are getting used to an easy life, drinking various alcoholic beverages, smoking cigarettes and chewing tobacco. Such harmful habits cause both economic and social harm to human health.

Keywords: hypodynamia, hypokinesia, system, emotional, mental, sleep, mutagen, alcoholism, stress, factors.

Physical education has a positive effect on people, strengthens their health, increases their working capacity, and helps them live longer. Therefore, in our republic, special attention is now being paid to physical education.

Health has always been of great importance in human life. The level of health has a significant impact on their professional abilities and creative growth.

In the minds of most students, the idea that physical education and sports are a factor in preventing diseases has not been formed. However, numerous studies conducted not only in our republic but also in foreign countries have proven that physical education has an effect on the human body and that they are an effective means of preventing various diseases.

With age and a violation of a healthy lifestyle, acquired diseases develop. From this, one can draw conclusions about the level of health depending on what kind of lifestyle a person leads.

Abu Ali ibn Sino is one of the founders of the science of health. The scientist paid great attention to the prevention and treatment of diseases, as well as to maintaining health.

He has repeatedly noted that regular exercise is a powerful factor in staying healthy and has focused on 7 factors for maintaining good health.

- Calmness;
- Eating habits;
- Keeping the body upright;
- Fresh air;
- Comfortable clothing;
- Physical activity;
- Fluency of mental activity (sleep and wakefulness).

Factors affecting health include:

1. External environmental factors. A person interacts with the external environment surrounding him. Social problems in living conditions can also affect people's health. The increasing influence of mutagenic (oncogenic, teratogenic) factors in the biosphere due to environmental pollution leads to an increase in hereditary diseases that are transmitted from generation to generation.

2. One of the factors that negatively affect health is improperly coordinated and irregular nutrition, which plays an important role in disrupting the normal functioning of the body and causing diseases. As a result of insufficient supply of nutrients to the body, its protective properties decrease, creating the basis for the occurrence of diseases, rapid fatigue leads to a decrease in working capacity. Inadequate nutrition of children delays growth and physical development.

3. Hypodynamia (Greek hypo-low, low and dynamic-strength) is insufficient muscle function, a decrease in the strength of contraction, usually due to constant sitting, reduced walking, transportation, low mobility, and a decrease in the load on the muscles, hypokinesia, i.e., a decrease in the person's motor activity, continues. Hypodynamia is also observed when a person is ill for a long time. As physical activity decreases, first energy expenditure decreases, and then the supply of tissues with blood, oxygen and nutrients worsens, as a result, the functioning of the body's control structures, i.e. the nervous and humoral systems, is disrupted. As a result, the signals from the muscles to the central nervous system decrease, which negatively affects the functioning of the brain, since muscle activity is very important in maintaining the tone of the central nervous system, regulating blood circulation and metabolism. If motor activity decreases sharply, changes are observed in the structure of the bones. Muscles atrophy, while adipose tissue increases, metabolic processes are disrupted, the functioning of the central nervous system changes, and the person quickly gets tired. The mechanism of the cardiovascular system, that is, the strength of heart contractions, decreases, and the condition of the blood vessels worsens: at first, this is expressed by shortness of breath when a person walks quickly, rapid heartbeat, and pain in the heart area during physical activity. Later, it causes atherosclerosis and hypertension. As a result of little movement and a lot of sitting, muscles become weak and relaxed early, a person's height becomes hunched, and the physiological aging process accelerates.

4. Harmful habits. Alcoholism is heavy drinking, which is the regular drinking of alcoholic beverages in excess of the norm to the extent that it harms the health and working capacity of some people, as well as the well-being of society. Alcoholism has a negative effect on all structures and organs of the human body. A person loses control of the amount of alcohol he drinks, not knowing the amount of alcohol he drinks, the activity of the central and peripheral nervous system is disrupted, mental illnesses, neuroses, etc. appear, and the functioning of internal organs fails. The toxic effects of alcohol lead to metabolic disorders and damage to the nervous system. People who drink a lot develop liver cirrhosis. Alcoholism also causes pancreatitis, diabetes, angina pectoris, and myocardial infarction. A person who drinks regularly becomes disabled and prematurely ages. In addition to alcoholism, harmful habits also include smoking and drug addiction. For example, let's take smoking tobacco products. Smoking causes bronchitis. As a result, the resistance of the lungs to various infectious diseases decreases. Nicotine contained in tobacco is a strong poison, 0.1 grams of which kills a person. This dose is contained in 20 cigarettes.

According to experts, 40-50% of the population's health depends on lifestyle. Harmful habits, poor nutrition, excessive consumption of alcohol and tobacco, prolonged sitting, stress, and environmental pollution lead to various diseases.

5. Psycho-emotional stress is one of the main factors affecting people's health in the modern era. The normal functioning of the human body depends on the level of its psyche. Any changes in mood and mood directly affect the functioning of organ systems. A person's mental depression, harsh words, and various negative events in life lead to stress. As a result of mental stress, people develop hypertension, angina pectoris and myocardial infarction, as well as mental illnesses and addictions. Psycho-emotional stress in women causes extremely dangerous complications, especially during pregnancy. Improving the quality of life of the population and stabilizing social conditions are the main conditions for preventing psycho-emotional stress. In conclusion, it can be noted that regular physical exercise helps to strengthen health, increase learning efficiency. Forms elements of physical culture. Health is the result of socio-economic, biological, ecological, medical and psycho-emotional influences and can be strengthened with the help of health-improving physical exercises. Regular exercise increases the body's natural resistance to the effects of the environment and infections. Currently, directions that satisfy the need for human health are becoming increasingly widespread (rhythmic gymnastics, rhythmic gymnastics, Chinese sign therapy, therapeutic and health-improving yoga, Chinese gymnastics.) are being implemented on a large scale.

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